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Abstract

This study contributes to innovation and its impacts on economic growth, particularly in trade reformation. The use of IOT platform in the service sector based on international experience found to be a resolution of the following issues: effectively and efficiently identify customer needs in the current industry, learn customer tastes, and provide customer facilities in retail outlets.

Key words

Commercial, service, IOT, innovation, entrepreneur, trade, auto-markets, Amazon Go.

Innovation is today's most actual topics that achieved much interest as a probable strategy of economic improvement and found to be of a significant importance in service sphere. So far, many surveys have been conducted, and the strength of innovative ideas/technologies in economic growth is recognized by many scientists. Some scholars stated that innovation is a

INNOVATIONS IN THE 3RD STAGE OF ECONOMY. IMPACTS OF DIGITALIZATION ON REFORMATION OF COMMERCIAL SPHERE

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada bugungi kundagi globallashuv jarayonlarida yoshlarimiz internet tarmoqlaridan to'g'ri foydalanish, information xurujlardan qanday ximoyalanih mumkinligi ularning salbiy oqibatlari, axborot xurujlarining turlari ularga qarshi kurashish usullari keltirilgan.

new combination of existing elements, while others defined it as basic mechanism that creates new ways of competing. Nowadays, this term comprises broader meaning than ever before. Innovation is therefore a broader idea than invention alone, because it also includes the development, application and/or commercialization of the invention.[1] Innovation relates to everything which refers to implementation of actions to meet client's needs by the most efficient way using better services, business plans and structures, novel inventions and technology and creating new or better goods for purchasers.[2] According to its concept and effect on existing inner and outer structure features innovations can be verified as followings:

- Technological innovation
- Economical innovation
- Management innovation
- Service innovation

In business sphere entrepreneur's basic goal is to achieve more incomes while investing less. There are two options in achieving higher results and increased income. The first one is, to make more investment into production process. The second one is, applying innovations, remaining the amount of inputs and obtaining more profit, which leads to company prosperity. By applying an innovative structure a country can benefit in many branches. By the virtue of innovations, country gains

- The increase in the level of employment
- Cost reduction
- Establishment of competitive positions among organizations
- Product/ service diversification
- Major economic growth
- New partnerships among organizations
- Enhanced level of brand and value recognition
- A novel dynamic product

It must be accentuated that service sector is a fundamental in both developed and developing countries as it is the catalyst for enriching the highest level of employment which is in turn, the primitive in development of macro economy. In past decade the content of service market has completed with new types of services, like: bank- finance, IT and insurance related ones. The role of advanced technologies had a tremendous effect on the evolution of this field, as, citizens provided with novel applicants, addressed to specialists in order to resolve an existing problem in their gadgets. Consistent with the statistic data informing about the speed of changes of market services, rate of acceleration in computer mending service and other

sustaining machines were just over 101,0%. Today, innovation appliance is resulting on production with dispatch, and guarantees market improvement, and boosts competitiveness of legged behind markets. The interest in perceiving how the innovation suits a vibrant business economy has extended in recent decades. Before scrutinizing the significance of innovation on economy and especially on service sector, the reformations and transformations implemented is needed to be emphasized.

In 5 initiatives of the President of Republic of Uzbekistan which was announced in 2019 year on 19th of March, the most unemployed part of society- women were highlighted along with the issue of joblessness. Supplying women with work is stated in 5th initiative. Through creating broad opportunities for women willing to work, the demand for accomplishment of domestic chores (cooking, cleaning, arranging) will experience a drastic increase. If it is undertaken at all, country will advantage in enhanced service and newly created workplaces.

Other ameliorations in this field took place thanks to the Service Development program, which embeds 2016-2020 years. Developments were seen in commercial, consumption, education, health, transportation related service sectors. One of the most fascinating results were in IT services, it attributed to the arrival of mobile/IP phones as well as the Internet to service sector.

IT has been gaining a perpetual power in 21st century. Today IT is called the enabler of business process. In order to lift the income level, IT can be exploited in third stage of economy (service). IT facilitates service process and makes it convenient

for both suppliers and purchasers. Still, it imposes some drawbacks not outweighing its advantages. So, what changes IT convey? Firstly, the job related drawbacks of IT in service will be mentioned:

☐ Computerizing the means of operation. Undoubtedly, it eliminates human labor from work. However, it takes place in institutions where the crucial portion of overall profit is distributed to workers.

☐ IT is the resolution to evade from intermediate- assistance. It augments the correspondence between producer and buyer, being more dependable and time-efficient.

Progressing to the subject of merits of useful and useable IT, the first and foremost thing to outline is-its strategic influence on economy development. The latest innovations came with digitalization and renamed as IOT and Big Data analytics. These modern technologies will have a significant contribution on increase of GDP level. In 2018 the capacity of service production copried10959.1 milliard of sum, where the most high percentage indicator was in trade sector, which is estimated 32.6%.[3] This dramatic increase in size is correlated with creation of new types of services, emergence of new commercial areas, construction of hotels, boosting the educational services and in particular the popularity of relatively new trading method, which is Internet-commerce. Previously mentioned digital technology will provide the flourishing future of traditional kind of trade, which is almost on the verge of replacement with Internet-markets. IOT (internet of things) is a new interconnection of technology announced as a next industrial development, which entails total changes

in markets. The arrival of the IOT has subserved as a driving force to many spheres of business to address to innovations and modern technology. Trading is not an exception. This branch has commenced an active utilization of IOT attributes. This machine gives an opportunity to promote the business efficiency, to scrutinize the demeanor of purchaser and create new business model. Today the established method of client captivation through commercial is not yielding an operative result. They do not allure the technologically educated Y generations' attention. Now, to take a next step forward and realize a trade promotion, vast refinements must be done. One of the solutions of mentioned issue is rooted in continuous elaboration and using up-and-coming IOT key. IOT is capable of accumulating information about purchasers, sellers' work-efficiency, managers' managerial qualities and also the transformation of goods. These features are the driver force in speeding the trade up. Moreover, an access to clients' demand reflected data is supplied by IOT. Inserting a special sensors and creating intellectual floors which track obtainers' movements throughout the shopping mall will enable providers to find out the needed information about their interests/demands. To make it more exact, knowing the most frequently visited and product obtained section of a mall, markets' territorial segmentation characteristics will be automatically identified, so the focusing on provision of most demanded goods will be easier. Another striking trait of IOT is face recognition. Noteworthy, this is broadly used in China and Great Britain (UK). System helps in supplying clients'

demands, offering them particular products according to their previous selections/style of goods that they have selected/ preferences and proposing a discount as that person is a permanent visitor of the shop. Succinctly, in retail IOT helps to make better decisions. Admittedly, the role of IOT is gradually rising. Before the ease correspondence between producer and obtainer via mobile programs or service calls were defined as facilitation. Getting better insight into development enlightens us about profound modifications. The illumination of intermediates is what expecting humanity in foreseeable future. The auto-markets the need for cashiers, sellers is eradicated. While entering the shop scanning the code is required, as customer installed a special program, get registered, entire picked commodities will be represented in installed app which also can be described as virtual basket and debited from shoppers' account. An exemplary pattern can be seen in one of the most acclaimed auto-markets Amazon Go. Now, Amazon Go

has its markets in San-Francesco, USA, Chicago and aimed to proliferation of robotic markets, constructing them all over the globe.

Uzbekistan is on the way of its development, took a step to digitalization and started the implementation of Digital Uzbekitan2030 program. Even through, the formulation of digital economy requires infrastructure, investments and labor resources digital transformation will be of an immense importance in improving quality of commodities and services, diminishing expenditures and completely getting disposed from corruption, the main enemy in creation investment alluring atmosphere.[4]

To sum up, a successful and sustainable business always correlated with innovative ideas and inventions. Remarkably, major economic growth even in deeply industrialized economics was attributed to innovation. If all putted targets will be auspiciously undertaken, in Uzbekistan the level of living conditions is expected to experience a severe elevation.

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